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Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering

Fundamentals of Networking Laboratory

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MOST INNOVATIVE PUBLIC UNIVERSITY IN THE U.S.
Reuters, 2017

STARTUP HUB OF UW

STARTUP COMPANIES
in 2018

BEST GRADUATE SCHOOL FOR 2020
US News & World Report

FEMALE FACULTY
Exceeds National Average

NEW FACULTY
for 2018-19 Academic Year

READY FOR:

OPEN IDEAS

x1 CHALLENGE

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

FUNDED BY

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OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Multimedia
Energy

CHALLENGE #19 - UW-5G-01

→ 5G Network Simulation and Test-Bed Integration

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

OBJECTIVES

1. Strengthen the position of open source network simulator ns-3 as the simulator of choice for 5G wireless network simulations.
2. Seek better alignment of ns-3 (in emulation mode) with experiments on wireless network test-beds (e.g. support for trace driven simulations and direct code execution).

SKILLS REQUIRED

1. Familiarity with ns-3, C/C++ and scripting (Python, Bash Shell).
2. ns-3 interfacing with HW test-bed, Software Defined networking.
3. Research Experience in a 5G technology area, knowledge on emerging standards.

